

Beyond Numerical Dominance: Presence, Influence and Strategic Behaviour in the Dutch States-General (1626–1630)

Rik Hoekstra, DHLab/Huygens Institute, KNAW, Amsterdam

The States-General, the main governing body of the Dutch Republic, met daily to issue resolutions on matters ranging from high politics (war and foreign policy) to low politics (passports and pensions). They recorded resolutions and propositions but not their deliberations. As the States-General consisted of deputies from the seven provinces and the provinces exerted influence through their deputies. However, the lack of recorded deliberations and of information about individual deputies, makes their contribution unclear (Thomassen, 2019). Furthermore, authors like Israel, Poelhekke and De Bruin often suggest that the presence of deputies is important for decision taking. However, these are impressions rather than concrete data (De Bruin 1991, Israel 1983, Poelhekke 1978).

For the study of modern parliaments, the organisation of political support using statistics has been quite an important topic, focusing on voting habits and agenda setting by parliamentary or committee presidents (e.g. Coomans, 1988, Baller 2017, Fowler 2006, Killerman 2016, Princen 2009). Early modern assemblies are not the same as modern ones. Both agenda setting and political support were important, but the methodology used by modern parliaments does not work well here (Kyle, 2002; Rodon & Paskalis, 2021).

In this paper we propose a computational method to explore the relationship between attendance and political influence. As deputy presence at sessions is the only available data, it becomes a crucial proxy for political influence. This topic has previously been explored in relation to Holland's numerical superiority (Nijenhuis, 2018; Gabriëls, 1989). These studies use absolute attendance counts and propose that Holland's numerical dominance was the expected model. However, actual attendance often diverges from this baseline. To quantify these deviations, we have devised the Relative Presence Profile (RPP), a metric that characterises both collective and individual attendance patterns. Our primary aim is to explore whether patterns of attendance that could contribute to the study of political influence in the Dutch Republic can be discerned beyond numerical dominance. Political influence and political networks were active on different levels, which we can describe as follows:

- *High politics*, dealing mainly with relations between the provinces and between the Republic and other powers.
- *Daily politics*, dealing with relations between the deputies of the various provinces, and provincial political tactics.
- *Low politics*, dealing with patronage, relations with individuals outside of the States General, and 'corruption' if we may describe the provision of services for money or favours as such.

The lobbying necessary to forge the political ties occurred at all levels.

This paper is a methodological contribution; explaining political influence is very difficult on the basis of statistical patterns alone, and is not yet the aim of this paper. We will provide an example for each of the different forms of political influence mentioned, mainly to

demonstrate how the RPP can provide additional insights beyond absolute numerical calculations, which almost invariably show Holland's dominance. The focus is on the period 1626–1630, comprising 19,133 resolutions over 1,430 sessions. This short period offers high-quality data and political stability, making it suitable for testing this methodology. The focus is on the period 1626–1630, comprising 19,133 resolutions over 1,430 sessions. This short period offers high-quality data and political stability, making it suitable for testing this methodology.

Relative Presence Profile - definition and calculation

The Relative Presence Profile (RPP) is a vector over one or a group of deputies (for instance those of a province) and can be thought of as how unusual or surprising the presence of a specific constellation of deputies was, if we take the expected presence as the norm. The expected presence is the average presence of the deputy or deputies concerned, for which we took the rolling mean over one year.

Formal definition

The RPP for an individual i is a T -dimensional vector of residuals between observed and expected presence across resolutions (dates). The collective RPP is the sum of the individual RPPs for all individuals concerned.

Let $A_{i,t}$ denote the observed presence (or attendance count) of person i at resolution t , and let $E_{i,t}$ denote the expected presence.

Where:

- $A_{i,t}$ — observed presence (or attendance count) of person i at time resolution t

- $E_{i,t}$ — expected presence for person i at time t , defined as the rolling mean over a window of w periods

$$A_{i,t} \in \{0,1\} \quad (\text{or } A_{i,t} \in \mathbb{Z}_{\geq 0} \text{ for collective attendance counts})$$

$$E_{i,t} = \frac{1}{w} \sum_{k=1}^w A_{i,t-k}$$

Here: $w = 1$ year (~ 365 days).

The residual $R_{i,t}$ is defined as:

$$R_{i,t} = A_{i,t} - E_{i,t}$$

Consequently, the RPP vector p_i is defined as:

$$p_i = (R_{i,1}, \dots, R_{i,T})$$

For a Provincial RPP, where P represents the province, the residual represents the deviation of the province's total attendance from its expectation:

$$p_P = (A_{P,1} - E_{P,1}, \dots, A_{P,T} - E_{P,T})$$

Collective RPP for provinces and deputies

The States-General sessions included deputies from seven provinces. Although each province held one vote (Thomassen 2019, 139), 147 deputies participated in the 1,430 sessions held between 1626 and 1630, with attendance varying from deputy to deputy, averaging 157 sessions per deputy. Graph 1 plots the attendance of the five deputies with the highest attendance per province. Generally, the provincial deputies provided continuous coverage of the sessions. In Friesland, however, coverage was poor during this period due to internal provincial disputes.

Graph 1. Actual attendance of top deputies per province

Forty-six deputies (almost a third of all attendees) served as president at least once between 1626 and 1630. A critical aspect of political influence is agenda setting, which was influenced by both the provinces (the principals of the deputies) and the Stadtholder Frederik Hendrik. Provinces had a primary deputy who attended frequently and served as president 80% of the time.

Graph 2 plots the provincial RPP for provincial presidency (see graph 2).

The graph suggests that deputies coordinated their attendance based on the president's provincial affiliation, possibly in order to form alliances or monitor opponents. For example, deviations involving presidents from Groningen may reflect ongoing disputes with Zeeland regarding unpaid taxes that benefited the admiralties. Splitting the data shows (graph 3) that there was higher attendance when 'head' deputies presided, even if the province did not exhibit this pattern (e.g., Haersolte, Noortwijk and Culemborg). No fixed set of deputies was responsible, and further elaboration is reserved for future work.

Graph 3. Deviation from expected province presence per individual president (faceted by president province)

Nijenhuis argued that the deputies who were trustees of Stadtholder Frederik Hendrik dominated the sessions. She lists his confidants: Van den Bouchorst (Noortwijk), Schaffer, Beaumont, Haersolte, Essen and Ploos (see also Israel 1983). However, the RPP in graph 4a shows that these delegates were less present than usual when Frederik Hendrik was mentioned. In contrast, deputies such as Renssen, Terculen and Vosbergen were present more often than expected (Graph 4b).

Graph 4. Deputies most/least associated with Frederik Hendrik mentions (top 10 positive (+) and bottom 10 negative (-) RPP)

Graph 4 - negative and positive RPP for Frederik Hendrik

A similar pattern emerges when we compare the RPP for the presidents with the counts (Graph 5). When Frederik Hendrik was mentioned, 'raw' presidency counts were dominated by the usual deputies. However, Haersolte and Schaffer presided less often, while Vosbergen presided more often than could be expected.

Graph 5. Frederik Hendrik president comparison: counts vs RPP

Graph 5 - President Counts vs RPP

While numerical dominance is important for major political issues, the RPP analysis shows that this dominance should be considered in more detail when comparing the expected and the actual attendance of deputies and presidents.

Individual attendance profiles

Individual attendance was influenced by various factors, including the employment of deputies by foreigners for influence puposes (De Bruin 1991, Janssen 2005). These deputies needed to be present or preside in order to influence the agenda or outcomes. We illustrate this using the French ambassadors Espesse (1626–1628) and Baugy (1628–1630).

Graph 6 shows that the vectors of their RPPs have a high cosine similarity of 0.94. This similarity is comparable to those of other major ambassadors (e.g., Vane, Camerarius), but low for others (e.g., Biscaino), and does not extend to the other 71 French individuals mentioned (mean similarity below 0.2). This indicates the potential for systematically comparing individual political influence.

Graph 6 - RPP for French ambassadors

Graph 7 plots the RPPs of deputies Veltdriel and Van Eck, regarding the resolutions concerning the top 30 ambassadors mentioned in resolutions during the period 1626-1630. Their

presence profiles were almost completely opposed. While it is difficult to elaborate on this without further research, which is beyond the scope of this paper, it is clear that the decision-making process of States-General regarding various ambassadors' affairs was influenced by different deputies.

Graph 7 - RPP profiles for two delegates at resolutions concerning ambassadors

Conclusion and further work

This paper has explored the potential of using the relative presence profile (RPP) to determine the presence and influence of individuals in the States-General sessions (1626–1630). This approach moves beyond previous attempts to measure influence based solely on numerical dominance, as it considers patterns in the presence of all deputies.

Analysis based on RPP for 'high politics' revealed strategic, collective patterns of presence among provinces and deputies. For 'low politics', the RPP analysis of relations with individuals shows wide diversity, indicating that political influence varied with the context in individual matters.

Future research will extend the analysis to consider all politics systematically and ultimately cover the entire period of the Republic (1576–1796). This will require the RPP measure to be adjusted for temporal dynamics.

References

[all urls accessed 202604]

Baller, Inger. 'Specialists, Party Members, or National Representatives: Patterns in Co-Sponsorship of Amendments in the European Parliament'. *European Union Politics* 18, no. 3 (2017): 469–90.

Bevan, Shaun, Enrico Borghetto, and Henrik Seeberg, 'The Politics of Parliamentary Agenda-Setting Styles', in *The Routledge Handbook of Policy Styles* (Routledge, 2021), pp. 244–56

De Bruin, Guido, *Geheimhouding En Verraad: De Geheimhouding van Staatszaken Ten Tijde van de Republiek (1600-1750)* (The Hague, 1991)

Coomans, APM. 'Parliamentary Agenda-Setting: A Comparative Legal Analysis'. *Maastricht Journal of European and Comparative Law* 5, no. 3 (1998): 262–76.

Fowler, James H. 'Connecting the Congress: A Study of Cosponsorship Networks'. *Political Analysis* 14, no. 4 (2006): 456–87

Israel, Jonathan I. 'Frederick Henry and the Dutch Political Factions, 1625-1642'. *The English Historical Review* 98, no. 386 (1983): 1–27. <https://www.jstor.org/stable/570162>.

Janssen, Geert H., *Creaturen van de Macht: Patronage Bij Willem Frederik van Nassau (1613-1664)* (Amsterdam, 2005)

Killermann, Kira. 'Loose Ties or Strong Bonds? The Effect of a Commissioner's Nationality and Partisanship on Voting in the Council'. *JCMS: Journal of Common Market Studies* 54, no. 6 (2016): 1367–83

Kyle, Chris R., 'Attendance, Apathy and Order? Parliamentary Committees in Early Stuart England', Kyle, Chris R., and Jason Peacey, eds. *Parliament at Work: Parliamentary Committees, Political Power, and Public Access in Early Modern England* (Woodbridge, 2002), pp. 43–58

Nijenhuis, Ida, 'Representation by Numbers: How Attendance and Experience Helped Holland to Control the Dutch States General (1626–1630)', in Damen, Mario, Jelle Haemers, and Alastair J. Mann, *Political Representation: Communities, Ideas and Institutions in Europe (c. 1200-c. 1690)* (Leiden, 2018), pp. 182–202

<https://www.researchgate.net/publication/327578802_Representation_by_Numbers_How_Attendance_and_Experience_Helped_Holland_to_Control_the_Dutch_States_General_1626-1630>

Poelhekke, J.J., *Frederik Hendrik: Prins van Oranje: Een Biografisch Drieluik* (Zutphen, 1978)

Princen, Sebastiaan, *Agenda-Setting in the European Union* (Springer, 2009) <<http://ndl.ethernet.edu.et/bitstream/123456789/59599/1/32.pdf>>

Rodon, Toni, and Tom Paskhalis, *Parliament Strikes Back: Agenda-Setting and Power Voids in Early Representative Assemblies*, 2021
<https://files.osf.io/v1/resources/qgu9c_v1/providers/osfstorage/618313670435d70034c03a29?action=download&direct&version=2>

Spanninga, H., 'Gulden vrijheid? : politieke cultuur en staatsvorming in Friesland, 1600-1640' (Uitgeverij Verloren, 2012) <<https://hdl.handle.net/1887/19168>>

Spanninga, H., 'Zonder Last of Ruggenspraak? De "Friese Vrijheid" En de Unie in de Eerste Decennia van de Zeventiende Eeuw', in *Nijenhuis, Ida, Joke Roelevink, Ronald Sluijter, De Leeuw Met de Zeven Pijlen. Het Gewest in Het Landelijk Bestuur* (Instituut voor Nederlandse Geschiedenis, 2010)

Thomassen, T.H.P.M., *Instrumenten van de Macht: De Staten-Generaal En Hun Archieven 1576-1796*, (Den Haag, 2009), 2 Vols. <URL:
https://resources.huygens.knaw.nl/retroboeken/instrumenten_macht>

Veenstra, Wietse, *Tussen gewest en Generaliteit: staatsvorming en financiering van de oorlog te water in de Republiek der Verenigde Nederlanden, in het bijzonder Zeeland (1586-1795)*, (dissertation VU, 2014 <url <https://research.vu.nl/nl/publications/0a92d8c3-60c8-42d6-ac54-898bb106f131>>